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Transitional Solutions and Achievement of VET Qualifications. A Case Study of the Canton of Ticino

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Abstract

Context: this contribution focuses on the group of youngsters living in the Swiss canton of Ticino who, after lower secondary school, attend one or more of the “transitional solutions” included in the Institute of Transition and Support (ITS). This institute aims at meeting the needs of youngsters with personal frailties, academic difficulties, social risk, cultural adaptation difficulties and complicated families and relationships. It supports them in the transition from compulsory school to post-compulsory education, promotes their integration into professional and social life and helps them in starting, maintaining and finishing a first basic vocational training and in containing the risk of failure in their training by providing them with educational support.

Approach: the pathways of all the youngsters who have started and attended at least one of the transitional solutions included in the ITS in Ticino in the period between the school year 2014/15 and 2016/17 (1280 youngsters) are examined through longitudinal analysis. Their access to the VET and the successful completion of the apprenticeship with the achievement of a certain qualification or, on the contrary, its interruption and the eventual reorientation or dropout by the end of 2020 are highlighted. Vocational pathways are put into relation to the type of transitional solution attended, which in turn depends on the needs and on characteristics of youngsters. Data used belong to the Ticino’s Department of Education, Culture and Sport, which has developed an application that makes available - in the form of a database - student-specific information, including data on the student’s past and current training, subjects studied and end of the year results.

Findings: of the 1280 youngsters who attended the ITS, 60 % have begun at least an apprenticeship in the three-year period 2016-2018. The outcome of the apprenticeship, i.e. whether it has been completed or interrupted or it is still in progress, varies according to the transitional solution attended. Almost 40 % of the apprenticeships begun by those who only attended the Orientation pre-apprenticeship or the Semester of motivation or the Integration pre-apprenticeship were completed by the end of 2020, while half were abandoned.

Conclusion: Transitional solutions are important footholds for young people in difficulty when accessing and completing an apprenticeship after compulsory school. However, 40 % of youngsters who have attended ITS do not have access to any VET, and in the cases in which they succeed to access, the percentage of interrupted apprenticeships is higher than in the total population and non-compliance with duties and disagreement between the contracting parties are more frequent reasons for dropout. Notwithstanding the ITS measures, a percentage of youngsters is not successful, probably because they lack social skills that cannot always be overcome.

Keywords: vocational education and training, transitions, longitudinal studies, inclusion

1 Introduction

Many authors emphasize the importance of vocational training for a fairer and more inclusive society (Collier, 2018; Major & Machin, 2018, 2020; Putnam, 2016; Reay, 2017; Sandel, 2020). Additionally, a number of studies show that the percentage of young people in VET programs has a positive effect on the upper secondary education completion rate (e.g. De Witte et al., 2013; Lamb, 2011; Lavrijsen & Nicaise, 2015). Basic vocational training, in fact, can be a positive alternative to general training by offering a more practical mode of learning and the possibility of moving towards specific professions and can play a crucial role in tackling early school leaving and promoting the inclusion of young people at risk (Cedefop, 2016).

A longitudinal study carried out in the Canton of Ticino, in Switzerland, on four cohorts of ca. 3000 youngsters each confirms the crucial role played by VET in qualifying young people from the most socially disadvantaged groups at greater risk of early school leaving. According to this study eight years after the end of compulsory school, more than half of young people from low social backgrounds and youngsters with a migrant background are in fact in possession of a vocational qualification (Zanolla, 2021). Despite the important equalization role played by the VET in upper secondary education, even in this kind of less elitist education, a sort of stratification is observed. The privileged social groups show, in fact, a higher propensity to achieve the vocational baccalaureate, which gives access to university tertiary education. The more disadvantaged ones, on the contrary, may struggle to find and complete an adequate apprenticeship and when they manage, they more frequently achieve a Federal VET certificate that does not allow access to tertiary education or a Federal VET diploma that only allows access to non-university tertiary education (Zanolla, 2021). This confirms what other authors have pointed out, namely that despite the increase in the share of working-class students attaining secondary vocational education they are less likely than better-off families 'children to graduate from tertiary education (Falcon, 2020).

This contribution focuses on the group of among the most vulnerable young people in the Canton of Ticino, that is, those who after lower secondary school attend one of the "transitional solutions" included in the Institute of Transition and Support. This institute aims at meeting the needs of youngsters with personal frailties, academic difficulties, social risk, cultural adaptation difficulties and complicated families and relationships. It supports them in the transition from compulsory school to post-compulsory training for integration into professional and social life, and it helps them in starting, maintaining and finishing a first basic vocational training and in containing the risk of failure in their training by providing them educational support. This contribution aims to present the "transitional solutions" included in the Institute of Transition and Support. Its goal is also to illustrate the vocational tracks followed by young people in Canton Ticino after having attended one or more of the above-mentioned transitional solutions.

2 The School Inclusion in the Canton of Ticino

Ticino is a canton characterized by a relatively comprehensive school system, where inclusion and equity are core values of school policy, while in Switzerland most cantons adopt a selective school system. Indeed, while most cantons adopt a system of early detection from the end of primary school, in Ticino all pupils from the age of three follow the same program until the end of the second year of lower secondary school, i.e. up to the ninth of the 11 years of compulsory school. During the last two years of lower secondary school, pupils take courses in mathematics, and German differentiate according to their level of competence (A courses with extended requirements or B courses with basic requirements). While remaining within the same heterogeneous classes, they are grouped differently, by skill level, for what concerns mathematics and German. Exceptionally, particularly weak students are allowed to complete their compulsory schooling by following differentiated activities expressly designed for them instead of certain subjects in which they would meet significant difficulties.

Although the differentiation in courses A and B in mathematics and German only relates to a marginal part of the compulsory school curriculum, it is of crucial importance in the determination of the possible choices of the students for the continuation of their training course. The attendance of courses with extended requirements (A) associated with a final grade average of at least 4,65 (on a rating scale of 2 to 6, where 4 represents sufficiency) are necessary conditions for access to high school, which issues gymnasium baccalaureate allowing access to the tertiary university level. Even to attend basic vocational training in a full-time school, students must complete the compulsory education and, depending on the school chosen, must meet certain conditions. In order to start basic vocational training in a company, on the contrary, it is sufficient to have completed compulsory school or to be at least 15 years old and have signed an apprenticeship contract with a company. Those who complete one of the two paths of basic vocational training (full-time or dual VET) and obtain a vocational baccalaureate have access to tertiary vocational education, a university tertiary education, while the achievement of the Federal vocational diploma only allows access to non-university tertiary education.

In general, in Ticino, it is possible to identify two types of institutional measures (all included in the framework of the Department of Education) aimed at promoting a successful transition to post-compulsory education: measures implemented during compulsory schooling, measures which take place during the transition from compulsory schooling to post-compulsory education and measures explicitly provided after compulsory education.

During compulsory schooling, there are four measures aimed at facilitating the transition to post-compulsory education:

- *curricular differentiation*, which consists in exempting 13-year-olds with difficulties from certain subjects and in entrusting them to a teacher who helps them to fill the scholastic and practical gaps that are essential to face the need of vocational training;
- *education to choices path*, which consists of activities aimed at developing the ability to perform choices;
- the *educator*, who carries out individual interventions of socio-educational accompaniment of students in school and extra-school settings with the goal of preventing and containing school discomfort;
- the *LIFT project* (it consists of the accompaniment of students with potential difficulties in vocational integration).

In addition to the measures implemented in compulsory school, there are federal or cantonal measures aimed at facilitating the transition to the VET or the attendance of this kind of education. In the last twenty years, in fact, more and more young people struggle to access the labour market, dropout of VET or do not pass the final exams. The causes are personal frailties, school obstacles, social risks, cultural adaptation difficulties, complicated family relationships, etc. To meet the needs of these young people, over time, it becomes necessary to establish specific measures that comply with the transition from compulsory education to basic vocational training and support them during training.

The main measures that take place after compulsory schooling are the transitional solutions organized by an appointed institute, the Institute of Transition and Support (ITS) whose aim is to coordinate the following intervention measures:

- *Case Management Vocational Training (CMFP)*, whose purpose is to identify pupils leaving compulsory school and young people up to 18 years considered at risk of dropout in the VET. It supports them in finding and completing an apprenticeship.

- *Orientation pre-apprenticeship* (PTO), which lasts one school year and attracts young people who failed to make a choice concerning training at the end of compulsory education or those who, in spite of making the first choice, did not succeed in being admitted to a school or could not find an apprenticeship in a company for the training they desired. Set up in 1994 with 12 students registered, enrolment for PTO has increased over the years and today stands at more than 200 units;
- *Integration pre-apprenticeship* (PTI), which is the main support measure for non-Italian-speaking young people who have not attended compulsory school in Ticino (or who have only minimally attended it) and who need to develop language skills necessary for starting an apprenticeship. Over the years, the PTI has differentiated its offer by establishing 3 paths, one directed to young people with schooling, one directed to non-literate or low-educated young people (*PTI and literacy*) and one for young adults between 21 and 25 years (*PTI for young adults*);
- *Semester of motivation* (SeMo), which is aimed at young people between 16 and 18 years of age who have interrupted an apprenticeship or a full-time VET and/or who have neither education nor professional and social integration prospects. The purpose of the service is to accompany these youngsters to find their way back to VET. The main goal of the SeMo is to define the individual training project in order to acquire and/or consolidate relational and social skills useful to professional integration, to acquire the skills necessary to find an apprenticeship, to improve school knowledge, to consolidate the ability to sustain work rhythms (respect for timetables, regular attendance and personal commitment).
- *Individual support in two-year training* (SiFb), which is a service that is mainly offered to young people who attend a two-year training with particular academic difficulties and problems adapting to the VET rhythms, whose educational success is seriously at risk of failure. The SiFb can also be requested for apprentices who follow the path to obtain the Federal VET diploma in the first year of training, and who need support aimed at identifying an adequate study method to allow the apprentice to continue the training independently.

3 Method

The pathways of all the youngsters who have started and attended at least one of the transitional solutions included in the Institute of Transition and Support in Ticino in the period between the school year 2014/15 and 2016/17 (1280 youngsters) are examined through longitudinal analysis. Their access to the VET and the successful completion of the apprenticeship with the achievement of a certain qualification or, on the contrary, its interruption and the eventual reorientation or dropout by the end of 2020 are highlighted. Vocational pathways are put into relation to the type of transitional solution attended, which in turn depends on the needs and on characteristics of youngsters. Data used belong to the Ticino's Department of Education, Culture and Sport, which has developed an application that makes available - in the form of a database called 'GAGI' - student-specific information, including some social and biographical details, data on the student's past and current training, subjects studied and end of the year results.

4 Findings

4.1 Pathways in the Vocational Training

1280 young people attended the ITS transitional solutions in the period between the 2014/15 school year and the 2016/17 school year. Among them, there are youngsters who did not access to any apprenticeship, youngsters who attended only one transitional solution,

youngsters who attended two (100 for example attended first the PTO and after the SeMo) or even three (25 people attended the PTI and literacy first, then the PTI and then the SiFb) or four (one person). In order to analyze the pathways in vocational training and the achievement of qualifications, it is necessary to keep in mind their different origins.

Of the 1280 youngsters who passed through ITS training, 732 have attended at least an apprenticeship in the three-year period 2016-2018, while 548 did not. The outcomes of the former vary according to the transitional solution attended (Figure 1). 42,5 % of the 438 apprenticeships begun by those who attended the PTO were completed while 11 % are still in progress and 47 % were abandoned by the end of 2020; these percentages amount to 35,5 %, 12 % and 52 % respectively for the 262 apprenticeships begun by youngsters who have only attended the SeMo. The lowest percentage of abandoned apprenticeships (40 %) can be observed among those who have only attended PTI although the 131 youngsters only started 70 apprenticeships. None of the 49 youngsters enrolled in the PTI and literacy managed to start an apprenticeship: this is because PTI and literacy is preparatory training for other transitional solutions or support measures and it is not aimed at direct entry into vocational training. The group of 25 youngsters who after the PTI and literacy attended the PTI and subsequently the SiFb, began 17 apprenticeships, of which 59 % were completed, 6 % are still in progress, and 35 % were interrupted.

Figure 1

ITS transitional solutions attended in Ticino during the period 2014/15 – 2016/17, apprenticeships begun in the period 2016-2018 and completed, interrupted or in progress by the end of 2020 (GAGI). Transitional solutions attended by less than 20 people were omitted.

ITS transitional solutions attended in the period 2014/15 – 2016/17	Number of youngsters who attended IST in the period 2014/15 – 2016/17	Number of apprenticeships started in the period 2016-2018	Percentage of completed apprenticeships	Percentage of apprenticeships which are still in progress	Percentage of interrupted apprenticeships
PTO	489	438	42.5 %	10.7 %	46.8 %
SeMo	335	262	35.5 %	12.2 %	52.3 %
PTI	131	70	42.9 %	17.1 %	40.0 %
PTO + SeMo	100	70	30.0 %	14.3 %	55.7 %
PTI and literacy	49	0	-	-	-
PTI and literacy + PTI	33	8	25.0 %	25.0 %	50.0 %
PTI and literacy + PTI + SiFb	25	17	58.8 %	5.9 %	35.3 %
PTO + SiFb	21	25	44.0 %	0.0 %	56.0 %
Total	1280	941	40.4 %	11.5 %	48.1 %

Of the 941 apprenticeships begun by the 1280 young people who attended the ITS, 61,5 % concerned the Industrial, Agricultural, Craft and Art Training Section and beyond 86 % a dual training, almost half were interrupted before the end, 40 % were completed, and 11,5 % were still in progress in December 2020. Even assuming that all the apprenticeships in progress are completed, the percentage of completed apprenticeships appears significantly lower than the corresponding one in the general population according to a recent study amounts to 68 % (Zanolla, 2017). The most common reason for dropout is professional reorientation (24 % of the cases of interruption), followed by poor results (22 %), personal reasons (17 %), and non-observance of duties (13 %) and the disagreement between the contracting parties (7 %).

Compared to the totality of the 13642 apprenticeships started in Ticino in the same three-year period 2016-2018, an over-representation of apprenticeships in the Industrial, Agricultural, Craft and Art Training Section as well as in the dual training and a higher dropout rate are observed. Among youngsters who have attended ITS non-compliance with duties and disagreement between the contracting parties are reasons that are more frequent for dropouts while vocational reorientation is less frequent (Figure 2).

Figure 2

Comparison between youngsters who have attended ITS and the whole population in Ticino for what concerns the pathways in the VET in the period 2016-2018 (GAGI).

		Young people who have attended ITS (941 apprenticeships)	Whole population (13462 apprenticeships)
VET sections	Section of industrial, agricultural, artisan and artistic training	61.5 %	47.1 %
	Section of commercial training and services	24.4 %	35.2 %
	Section of health and social training	14.0 %	17.6 %
VET type	Dual VET	86.4 %	65.1 %
	Full time VET	13.6 %	34.9 %
Apprenticeship outcome by the end of 2020	In progress	11.5 %	23.1 %
	Completed	40.4 %	44.7 %
	Dropout	48.1 %	32.2 %
More frequent reasons for dropout	Vocational reorientation	24.0 %	30.8 %
	Poor results	21.7 %	21.0 %
	Non-compliance with duties	12.9 %	10.1 %
	Personal reasons	16.6 %	16.4 %
	Disagreement between the contracting parties	6.9 %	5.2 %

Of the 361 youngsters who quit the first apprenticeship, 198 (55 %) do not start a second one, 78 (22 %) start a second apprenticeship and drop out while 69 (19 %) complete it (Figure 3). In this case, there is a considerable deviation from the general population, which from another study does not appear to undertake a second apprenticeship after having quit the first one in only 13 % of cases (Zanolla, 2017). Of the 304 who had completed the first training, 285 (94 %) did not start a second apprenticeship, 6 started and completed it (2 %) and 5 (2 %) started and stopped it. Enrollment in a second apprenticeship after completing the first is, in almost all cases linked to the desire to achieve a Federal VET diploma after a Federal VET certificate. Young people who have attended ITS and completed their first apprenticeship and obtained a Federal VET diploma do not generally choose to undertake a second one, at least not in the time frame considered. This type of choice, on the other hand, is quite common in the general population, as it constitutes a way to consolidate one's profile and make oneself more attractive in the labour market (Zanolla, 2017). Two people enrolled in four apprenticeships within the period considered, without having completed any of the previous ones: if the professional reorientation is not in itself a negative fact, since it is a young population that is still defining its own professional project and life, too many breakups are an indicator of difficulty in adapting to the work context. In this case, there is a significant deviation from the general population, in which only 13 % of those who dropout of the first apprenticeship does not undertake a second one (Zanolla, 2017). Of the 304 who complete the first apprenticeship, 285 (94 %) do not start

a second apprenticeship, 6 started and completed it (2 %), and 5 (2 %) started it and dropout. Enrollment in a second apprenticeship after completing the first one is in almost all cases linked to the desire to achieve a Federal vocational diploma after a Federal VET certificate. Young people who have attended ITS and completed their first apprenticeship and obtained a Federal vocational diploma do not generally choose to undertake a second one, at least not in the time frame considered. This type of choice, on the other hand, is quite common in the general population, as it constitutes a way to consolidate one's profile and make oneself more attractive in the labour market (Zanolla, 2017). Two people enrolled in four apprenticeships within the period considered without completing any of them: if the vocational reorientation is not in itself a negative fact, since youngsters are still defining their own vocational project, too many breakups are an indicator of difficulty in adjusting to the work environment.

Figure 3

Vocational and non-vocational pathways undertaken by youngsters after the attendance of ITS in the period 2014/15 – 2016/17 (GAGI).

4.2 The Achievement of VET Qualifications

This paragraph will illustrate the qualifications achieved by the end of 2020 by young people who in the period between 2014/15 and 2016/17 have started one or more ITS transitional solutions (Figure 4). Transitional solutions that concerned less than 20 cases were omitted.

Figure 4

VET qualifications achieved by the end of 2020 by youngsters who attended one or more ITS transitional solutions in the period 2014/15 – 2016/17 (GAGI). Transitional solutions attended by less than 20 people were omitted.

ITS transitional solutions attended in the period 2014/15 - 2016/17	Vocational baccalaureate	Federal VET diploma	Federal VET certificate	Apprenticeship in progress	Dropout	Apprenticeship never started	Total
SeMo (335)	1.5 %	36.4 %	6.0 %	8.4 %	20.6 %	27.2 %	100.0 %
PTO (489)	1.4 %	37.6 %	12.1 %	8.4 %	19.6 %	20.9 %	100.0 %
PTI (131)	0.8 %	22.1 %	6.9 %	7.6 %	9.9 %	52.7 %	100.0 %
PTO + SeMo (100)	0.0 %	17.0 %	6.0 %	10.0 %	30.0 %	37.0 %	100.0 %
PTI & literacy + PTI (33)	0.0 %	3.0 %	3.0 %	6.1 %	6.1 %	81.8 %	100.0 %
PTO + SiFb (21)	0.0 %	0.0 %	61.9 %	0.0 %	33.3 %	4.8 %	100.0 %
PTI & literacy + PTI + SiFb (25)	0.0 %	0.0 %	40.0 %	4.0 %	16.0 %	40.0 %	100.0 %
PTI & literacy (49)	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	100.0 %	100.0 %

The upper part of Figure 4 shows the transitional solutions after whose attendance the highest percentages of qualifications were achieved. Of the 335 youngsters who have only attended the SeMo, 1,5 % have obtained a vocational baccalaureate, 36 % a vocational diploma, 6 % a Federal vocational certificate, 8 % are still attending the VET, 21 % have started and subsequently quit the apprenticeship, and the remaining 27 % have never started it.

The 489 who attended the PTO achieved in 1 % of the cases a vocational baccalaureate, in 38 % a Federal vocational diploma, in 12 % a Federal vocational certificate while 8 % are still in training, 20 % dropped out, and the remaining 21 % have never started this kind of education.

Those who have attended the PTI (131 youngsters) in 1 % of the cases achieved a vocational baccalaureate, in 22 % a Federal vocational diploma and in 7 % a Federal vocational certificate. 8 % of them are still in training, 10 % have dropped out, and 53 % have never started the VET.

The lower part of the figure concerns those who have attended the PTI and literacy with or without the attendance of further transitional solutions. Of the 49 subjects who attended the PTI and literacy, none has started an apprenticeship: this is due to the fact that, as above mentioned, PTI and literacy it is not aimed at direct entry into vocational training. Youngsters who have attended a PTI and literacy and other measures such as PTI and SiFb in 40 % of the cases achieve a Federal vocational certificate, in 4 % they are still in training, in 16 % they have dropped out of the VET and in 40 % never started it. It is important to remember that this is a particularly vulnerable segment of youngsters with little or no schooling at all.

The support system to transition I is well developed in Ticino since there are numerous propositions, especially for the more vulnerable who often experience greater difficulty during this stage. The transitional solutions are important footholds for young people with difficulty when accessing and completing an apprenticeship after compulsory school.

The analyses presented here show that of the 1280 youngsters who passed through ITS training in the period 2014/15 and 2016/17, 60 % have attended at least an apprenticeship in the three-year period 2016-2018 with an outcome which varies according to the transitional solution attended (which varies according to the youngsters' needs). Almost 40 % of the apprenticeships begun by those who only attended the PTO or the SeMo or the PTI were completed by the end of 2020, while half were abandoned. Among youngsters who have attended

ITS the percentage of interrupted apprenticeships is higher than in the total population and non-compliance with duties and disagreement between the contracting parties are more frequent reasons for dropout. This suggests that notwithstanding the ITS measures, a percentage of youngsters is not successful and remains at a standstill, probably because they have a lack of social skills that cannot always be overcome.

Further research is needed on the impact of each of the ITS transitional solutions through methods of counterfactual impact evaluation and on the reasons that lead young people to interrupt the apprenticeship before the end.

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Biographical notes

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